

Note on Contributors

(In order of Appearance)

Dr. Mausumi Sen Bhattacharjee is an Associate Professor and former Head of the Department of English, The Sanskrit College and University, Kolkata. She has been teaching for the last twenty-five years. She worked at Visva Bharati as Asst. Lecturer in 2000. She was formerly employed at Bolpur College, affiliated to Burdwan University (November 2000 – July 2019). She completed her MPhil in 2002 on the “Generic Lineage of three plays by Harold Pinter” from Jadavpur University. Her doctoral dissertation on the “Representation of the Masquerade in the novels of Eliza Heywood, Fanny Burney and Elizabeth Inchbald” got awarded in 2010 from Jadavpur University. She is a recipient of two UGC Minor Research projects in 2004 and 2018 respectively that were successfully completed. She has published both nationally and internationally and her areas of interest include works on the films of Ghatak and Ray, Gender studies, Travel writing and travelogues, Conflict zone and border studies, Partition literature, British women writings and Culture studies. She can be contacted at mausumisen@gmail.com.

Debapriya Sarkar is a postgraduate in English Literature from the University of Delhi and is currently working as an independent researcher. Being an ardent intersectional feminist at heart, her interest lies in the field of Gender and Sexuality, Intimacy Studies, and Trauma/Memory Studies, especially pertaining to South-Asian fiction. She has presented papers on these areas in several international and national conferences and has also co-authored a paper for a peer-reviewed journal, *Critical Imprints*. Recently, she has laid the foundation for an all-women’s support group called ‘Sakhee’ based in Kolkata. Through her scholarly enquiry, she envisions contributing to the discourse of camaraderie and healing in an era of metamodernism. She can be contacted at debapriya00@gmail.com

Dr. Prayag Ray is an Assistant Professor of English at St. Xavier’s University, Kolkata. After studying at Jadavpur University and Jawaharlal Nehru University, he completed his PhD at Queen’s University, Belfast. His thesis explored representations of Hinduism in British literature of the long eighteenth century. His research interests include Fantasy fiction, Children’s literature, Popular culture, Postcolonial studies, and Eighteenth-century literature. He has published work in *Postcolonial Studies*, *Journal for Eighteenth-Century Studies*, and *Poetry Ireland Review*. He has written book chapters that have appeared in edited volumes published by Springer, Routledge, and Atlande (Paris). He can be contacted at prayag.ray@sxuk.edu.in.

Anushka Saha is pursuing a postgraduate degree in English Literature at Jadavpur University. She has been awarded for academic excellence in B.A.

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Stuti Chatterjee is also a postgraduate student of English Literature at Jadavpur University. She completed her Bachelor's degree from Bethune College, Kolkata. She has been recognised with numerous awards for academic excellence throughout her Bachelor's degree. Her research interests include Popular literature, Partition literature, Romanticism, Subaltern studies and Women's writing. She can be contacted at stutchatterjee2106@gmail.com.

Dr. Diana Turken was born and raised in Los Angeles and is currently serving as a lecturer in English at California Polytechnic State University. She earned her MFA degree in Poetry at Mills College and her PhD from the University of Rhode Island. Her critical work is focused on American literature of the long 20th Century, Critical Studies, and Urban Studies, and her dissertation is a critical investigation of contemporary imaginings of the American West. Additionally, her poetic work explores themes of modern and historical myth making, borders, and migration. She can be contacted at dianaturken@gmail.com.

Samavia Zia is a human rights activist, MUN award winner, writer, researcher, and former Lecturer at PUCIT. Her work explores decoloniality, feminism, and their intersections, with recent interests in translation and museum studies. She has completed three UN projects, presented at more than eight international conferences, and published in Y-Category journals and global anthologies. Samavia holds key roles in multinational NGOs and contributes as a poet to both national and international platforms. An MUN Award Winner and IFREL member, she was nominated for and received the "Emerging Scholar Award," by University of Ohio, recognizing her growing influence in interdisciplinary literary research. She can be contacted at samaviazia2@gmail.com.

Dr. Kehinde Oyetimi is a lecturer in the Department of English, University of Ibadan. His research focuses on oral literature, gender dialectics, performance studies, and cultural analysis. He explores how folktales, myths, and indigenous performances reflect and shape societal values, with particular attention to gender representation and power dynamics. His work engages with the roles of griots, praise singers, and oral artists as cultural custodians. Dr. Oyetimi is also interested in the intersections of tradition and modernity, examining how oral narratives adapt in contemporary contexts, including digital media and AI-assisted storytelling in African oral cultures. He can be contacted at joyetimi2002@gmail.com.

Dr. Fatima Zohra Hamrat holds a PhD in LLCER (*Langue, Littérature, Culture Étrangère et Régionale*), specializing in colonialism, postcolonial studies, and political history. Beyond literature, her research explores civilization, political

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Dr. Claudia Zucca holds a Ph.D. at Trinity College Dublin. She is a Professor in Primary Education at the Faculty of Humanities, a Professor of English in International Relations at the Faculty of Political Science at the University of Cagliari, and an external member of the board of examiners at the University of Madras. She is a member on the advisory board (IAB) for *Horizon Journal of Humanities & Social Sciences Research* (JHSSR) since 2022, and an advisory board member in literature and media at the Museum of Childhood Ireland since 2024. She has participated in international conferences, and has published articles on translanguaging, feminist and gender representations and rights, incarceration and human rights in South Africa. She can be contacted at claudia.zucca@unica.it.

Dr. Barbara Gabriella Renzi is a psychologist, philosopher, and academic with dual PhDs and extensive teaching experience across Europe. She lectures in psychology, philosophy, and business studies at institutions in Germany, Italy, and the UK. A published author and researcher, her work spans cognitive sciences, education, counselling, and eco-linguistics. Dr. Renzi is a licensed psychologist, CBT therapist, and a member of major international counselling and psychotherapy associations. Fluent in various languages, she is passionate about intercultural dialogue, mental health, and sustainability. Her scholarly output includes numerous peer-reviewed publications, books, and conference presentations on identity, trauma, and metaphor in education and society. She can be contacted at barbararenzi@outlook.com.

Loris Luo holds a Bachelor's degree in Media and Communication Studies and is currently pursuing a Master's in Liberal Studies at The New School. She has extensive experience in journalism, feature writing, and publishing across various media platforms. In addition to her work in media, she organizes cultural events focused on social justice and human rights. Through her interdisciplinary approach, she explores the intersections of media, politics, and social movements, using storytelling as a tool for advocacy and collective empowerment. She can be contacted at luol297@newschool.edu or 1043835861@qq.com.
